

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/wad
hash://md5/0edd01167678b3dfb7525c844b77bb0b

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/wad`, has fingerprint `hash://md5/0edd01167678b3dfb7525c844b77bb0b`, is 19.8MiB in size and contains 24,064 interactions with 5 unique types of associations (e.g., eats) between 2,162 primary taxa (e.g., *Eratoneura acantha* (Ross & DeLong, 1950)) and 1,708 associated taxa (e.g., `1e55928f-1c9b-4e7f-85af-a89d50e2c2b2`). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

World Auchenorrhyncha Database <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/wad/archive/17b6f241c8c2026-06-06T11:13:05.510Z> hash://md5/0edd01167678b3dfb7525c844b77bb0b

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5

tool name	version
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 19.8MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/wad

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/wad \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/wad \
  > interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/wad \
  | nomer append col \
  > name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/wad`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/wad`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/wad`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/wad`)

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/wad`, has fingerprint hash://md5/0edd01167678b3dfb7525c844b77bb0b, is 19.8MiB in size and contains 24,064 interactions with 5 unique types of associations (e.g., eats) between 2,162 primary taxa (e.g., *Eratoneura acantha* (Ross & DeLong, 1950)) and 1,708 associated taxa (e.g., 1e55928f-1c9b-4e7f-85af-a89d50e2c2b2).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Erythridula ulmosa (Ross & DeLong, 1953)	eats	f84e273b-4ee3- 48ae-b04e- dc3c139a86e7	H.H. Ross, L.J. Stannard
Eratoneura uncinata (Beamer, 1931)	eats	39430fe1-dfe0- 4fa6-84ac- 56a92ae2e8e4	H.H. Ross, L.J. Stannard
Eratoneura uncinata (Beamer, 1931)	eats	39430fe1-dfe0- 4fa6-84ac- 56a92ae2e8e4	Herbert Holdsworth Ross R.A. Evers
Eratoneura uncinata (Beamer, 1931)	eats	39430fe1-dfe0- 4fa6-84ac- 56a92ae2e8e4	H.H. Ross, W.R. Richards

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	21838
adjacentTo	1934
interactsWith	158
hasHost	133
visitsFlowersOf	1

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Eratoneura acantha (Ross & DeLong, 1950)	719
Eratoneura carmini (Beamer, 1929)	650
Eratoneura gilesi (Hepner, 1966)	617
Eratoneura arta (Beamer, 1931)	574
Eratoneura adunca (Beamer, 1932)	570
Eratoneura longa (Knull, 1955)	532
Eratoneura millsi (Ross & DeLong, 1950)	530
Empoasca (Empoasca) fabae (Harris, 1841)	481
Eratoneura gemina (McAtee, 1920)	468
Eratoneura patris (Ross & DeLong, 1953)	454
Eratoneura usitata (Beamer, 1932)	368

sourceTaxonName	count
Eratoneura campora (Robinson, 1924)	361
Eratoneura parva (Beamer, 1932)	345
Eratoneura bigemina (McAtee, 1920)	335
Eratoneura affinis (Fitch, 1851)	281
Eratoneura maga (Knull, 1951)	270
Eratoneura penesica (Beamer, 1931)	235
Eratoneura firma (Beamer, 1932)	230
Eratoneura basilaris (Say, 1825)	230

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
1e55928f-1c9b-4e7f-85af-a89d50e2c2b2	1806
8375eb7a-c4db-43a6-bda0-de912f29de54	1410
d8858587-8500-4372-a55a-079722542641	1070
13a582fd-5025-4b1a-9503-99c3fcce2ea2	906
4250a0b4-ab18-43af-a898-edd1d3b394a5	756
3bc07f79-219a-451e-9d92-6720696b9a6a	676
f07c137c-8d34-4f3e-b460-b082e7c80ed6	634
07257a06-dd27-4196-be77-17646735213e	583
d0fef104-a7db-4280-b6b8-4a85efb9a4c1	561
71adb45d-1b37-4fe5-9283-67c4304c2f4b	514
dc29a848-3940-475d-9e29-82dd09c089f1	513
269f6eb9-854c-489c-88fe-6a64037b7544	461
ece42758-2845-47df-9ec7-ccf070101c91	435
a26a1554-ee6b-48f0-b350-33f65d980197	375
e7e8b282-eb0d-4878-be67-c7c2a6e076d6	319
f84e273b-4ee3-48ae-b04e-dc3c139a86e7	315
c64fe4e9-c40a-4b3a-9b7f-1097e1432f89	308
4a49de66-9f89-4603-a08f-b250dc71645b	296
d6283358-2bee-4ed4-8157-5bff16f81ccf	291

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Eratoneura arta (Beamer, 1931)	eats	13a582fd-5025-4b1a-9503-99c3fcce2ea2	440

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Eratoneura gilesi (Hepner, 1966)	eats	1e55928f-1c9b-4e7f-85af-a89d50e2c2b2	399
Eratoneura millsii (Ross & DeLong, 1950)	eats	8375eb7a-c4db-43a6-bda0-de912f29de54	393
Eratoneura patris (Ross & DeLong, 1953)	eats	1e55928f-1c9b-4e7f-85af-a89d50e2c2b2	363
Eratoneura longa (Knull, 1955)	eats	d8858587-8500-4372-a55a-079722542641	336
Eratoneura acantha (Ross & DeLong, 1950)	eats	1e55928f-1c9b-4e7f-85af-a89d50e2c2b2	255
Eratoneura usitata (Beamer, 1932)	eats	13a582fd-5025-4b1a-9503-99c3fcce2ea2	252
Eratoneura adunca (Beamer, 1932)	eats	1e55928f-1c9b-4e7f-85af-a89d50e2c2b2	247
Eratoneura parva (Beamer, 1932)	eats	8375eb7a-c4db-43a6-bda0-de912f29de54	233
Eratoneura acantha (Ross & DeLong, 1950)	eats	d8858587-8500-4372-a55a-079722542641	188
Eratoneura adunca (Beamer, 1932)	eats	d8858587-8500-4372-a55a-079722542641	160
Eratoneura carmini (Beamer, 1929)	eats	f07c137c-8d34-4f3e-b460-b082e7c80ed6	149
Eratoneura igella (Ross & DeLong, 1950)	eats	8375eb7a-c4db-43a6-bda0-de912f29de54	130
Eratoneura staminea (Knull, 1954)	eats	1e55928f-1c9b-4e7f-85af-a89d50e2c2b2	130
Eratoneura firma (Beamer, 1932)	eats	f07c137c-8d34-4f3e-b460-b082e7c80ed6	113

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Eratoneura triangulata (Beamer, 1931)	eats	a26a1554-ee6b- 48f0-b350- 33f65d980197	104
Eratoneura tammiana (Ross & DeLong, 1953)	eats	8375eb7a-c4db- 43a6-bda0- de912f29de54	100
Eratoneura unica (Beamer, 1932)	eats	07257a06-dd27- 4196-be77- 17646735213e	100
Eratoneura restricta (Beamer, 1932)	eats	07257a06-dd27- 4196-be77- 17646735213e	91

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life [download svg](#)

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
```

```

PROJECTION
  "init=epsg:4326"
END
LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
  NAME      "modis_nasa"
  TYPE      RASTER
  OFFSITE   0 0 0
  STATUS    ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
  CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR      232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
END
LAYER
  NAME "indexed-interactions"
  TYPE POLYGON
  STATUS ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
  CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
  DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
      DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 4.0217266644137775
      RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
  END
END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Bb ae57 a8f d3612aaab	NONE	col	Bb ae57 a8f d3612aaab
Fa1d dd01 ffc bf12 fa63d1bf2359	NONE	col	Fa1d dd01 ffc bf12 fa63d1bf2359
a927f f5f6 aa8b fb6c11	NONE	col	a927f f5f6 aa8b fb6c11
a93 f189 f5b dd3 b6df9f9a000e	NONE	col	a93 f189 f5b dd3 b6df9f9a000e

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	1206
col	family	7
col	genus	249
col	kingdom	1
col	species	1914
col	subspecies	60
col	tribe	1
col	variety	7
discoverlife	NA	3433
gbif	NA	1317
gbif	family	7
gbif	genus	249
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	species	1816
gbif	subspecies	52
gbif	variety	7
itis	NA	2940
itis	family	7
itis	genus	132
itis	kingdom	1
itis	species	336
itis	subspecies	11
itis	variety	6
mdd	NA	3432
ncbi	NA	2723
ncbi	family	6
ncbi	genus	218
ncbi	species	477
ncbi	subgenus	2
ncbi	subspecies	7
ncbi	varietas	1
pbdb	NA	3287
pbdb	family	7
pbdb	genus	103
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	species	34
tpt	NA	3432
wfo	NA	2985
wfo	family	6

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
wfo	genus	133
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	297
wfo	subspecies	13
wfo	variety	4
worms	NA	3278
worms	family	3
worms	genus	87
worms	kingdom	1
worms	species	63
worms	variety	1

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	1239
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2900
col	SYNONYM_OF	474
discoverlife	NONE	4163
gbif	NONE	1353
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2881
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	574
itis	NONE	3520
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	595
itis	SYNONYM_OF	76
mdd	NONE	4160
ncbi	NONE	2985
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	60
ncbi	SAME_AS	1129
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	2
pbdb	NONE	3854
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	302
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	9
tpt	NONE	4160
wfo	NONE	3648
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	137

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	433
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	35
worms	NONE	3891
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	214
worms	SYNONYM_OF	73

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-08T09:47:04Z	note	target taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-06-08T09:47:04Z	note	target taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-06-08T09:47:04Z	note	target taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-06-08T09:47:04Z	note	target taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
target taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder	21835
source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder	53
found unsupported interaction type with name: [roadside]	20
found unsupported interaction type with name: [coll.]	19

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-08) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

filename	description
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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